

Evaluation of the Free Halal Certification Program (SEHATI) for Processed Livestock Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) in Blitar Regency

Nur Khasanah¹, Siti Azizah^{2*}, Agus Susilo³

¹Postgraduate, Faculty of Animal Science, Universitas Brawijaya, Jl. Veteran Malang, 65145, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecture on Faculty of Animal Science, Universitas Brawijaya, Jl. Veteran Malang 65145, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The free halal certification program (SEHATI) aims to support the Indonesian government's goal of having one million halal-certified food and beverage products by 2024 by accelerating the rate of halal certification through the SEHATI program. Blitar Regency has 33,932 micro and small enterprises (MSEs), but only 389 have halal certification, including egg and milk processing products. The research aims to determine the effectiveness of the SEHATI program's implementation for livestock processing MSEs in Blitar Regency. The study uses mixed methods. Data were collected through questionnaires to 12 respondents, including stakeholders and livestock processing business actors. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive analysis and logic model evaluation analysis. The effectiveness of the SEHATI program's implementation was the data collected in the research. The results show that the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency, through socialization and assistance to livestock processing business actors, is effective. The logic model evaluation on all indicators shows that the business actors are well-informed, understand well, and strongly agree with the input, activities, output, and outcome of the SEHATI program. The conclusion of the research is that the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency significantly benefits in raising awareness, understanding, compliance, and the number of halal products from egg and milk processing business actors. This indicates the effectiveness of this program in helping livestock processing business actors obtain halal certification.

KEYWORDS: Effectiveness, Livestock processing, MSEs, SEHATI program.

INTRODUCTION

The issuance of Law (UU) Number 33 of 2014 concerning Halal Product Assurance (JPH) was a regulation that mandated goods and services traded in Indonesia to have halal certification. Donny and Kurniawan (2023) stated that although the JPH Law had been effective since 2019 and the BPJPH Agency had been established since October 2017, in reality, many products did not undergo the halal product certification process. Blitar Regency was known for its significant livestock potential. According to data from the Department of Animal Husbandry and Fisheries (2021), livestock production in Blitar Regency included meat, eggs, and milk commodities with significant production figures. Meat production reached 19,461,258, eggs reached 179,962,404, and milk reached 40,312,385, leading many micro and small enterprises (MSEs) to process livestock products such as eggs and milk in Blitar Regency, which had great development potential.

Data (BPS, 2022) showed that out of a total of 33,932 categories of micro and small processing businesses in Blitar Regency, only a small portion had halal certification, namely 389 MSEs, including processed egg and milk products, indicating that many MSEs still needed support and motivation to obtain halal certification. The obligation for halal certification on products circulating was based on Government Regulation No. 39 of 2021 with a phasing period on October 17, 2024. The Blitar Regency Government utilized the Free Halal Certification Program (SEHATI) as a form of support and motivation for MSEs to obtain halal certification easily. Based on research by Rachmaniah, et al. (2024), although the SEHATI Program had been initiated by the government since 2021, this program was relatively unknown to MSEs as the subjects of halal certification; hence, P3H needed to assist SMEs.

Based on research by Ningrum (2022), the problems faced by business actors regarding the obligation for halal certification included: lack of socialization about halal certification, limited economic capacity of business actors to manage halal certification, limited production facilities to meet halal production process requirements, and the mindset of business actors on the importance of halal certification, thus there was a need for wider outreach and socialization, the formation of financial assistance or subsidies, provision of easier access to production facilities, and the development of training programs. Based on research by Anas, et al. (2023), the implementation of the SEHATI program faced various obstacles experienced by business actors, including: difficulty accessing the

internet, creating an NIB on the OSS web, filling out business actor data on the SiHalal application, searching for Halal Material Certificate numbers on the Halal Indonesia web, and compiling the SJPH manual. Business actors also did not fully understand the requirements of the SEHATI program. Based on the explanation, it was important to evaluate the SEHATI program.

To understand the requirements of the SEHATI program, it is important to evaluate the SEHATI program implemented by the Blitar Regency Government. This evaluation is needed to determine how far the program has succeeded in achieving its goals and to identify the obstacles faced by livestock processing MSEs in obtaining halal certification.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted from July to August 2023 in Blitar Regency, involving stakeholders participating in the SEHATI program and small and micro enterprises (SMEs) processing livestock products such as eggs and milk. The research subjects used as respondents in this study included 4 stakeholder respondents: the Ministry of Religious Affairs (Kemenag) Blitar Regency, the Cooperative Department (Dinkop) Blitar Regency, LP3H of Balitar Islamic University (Unisba), and LP3H of Maulana Malik Ibrahim Islamic University (Uinma), as well as 8 respondents from livestock processing SMEs. The study utilized mixed methods, with an explanatory design research approach. The researcher collected and analyzed qualitative data, followed by the collection and analysis of quantitative data. The qualitative method was used to analyze the implementation of the program using open-ended questionnaires, while the quantitative method employed closed-ended questionnaires with Likert scale measurements on the variables of input, activities, output, and outcome. The data sources used consisted of primary data obtained directly through interviews with questionnaires to respondents, and secondary data obtained from reference books and articles. The data analysis employed descriptive analysis and logic model evaluation analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Implementation of the Free halal Certification Program (SEHATI)

The implementation of the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency is carried out through socialization and assistance to livestock processing SMEs. Based on the interview results, the program aims to support the Indonesian government's goal of having 1 million halal-certified food and beverage products by 2024. All products circulating or sold in Indonesia must be halal-certified, as an effort to accelerate the rate of halal certification among SMEs that do not yet have halal certification. This aligns with Kurniawan's (2021) opinion, which states that the objectives of the SEHATI program include: increasing the awareness of SME actors about the importance of halal certification and halal labels for business actors to accelerate business growth, increasing public awareness about the importance of consuming halal products, strengthening halal products produced by SMEs, increasing the number of SMEs that meet halal requirements, and enhancing the added value and competitiveness of SME products in both local and international markets..

The SEHATI program in Blitar Regency needs to be implemented because many livestock processing SMEs do not yet have halal certification. There is a policy requiring halal certification for products circulating in modern markets; if SME products do not have halal certification, the SME actors will receive warnings. This aligns with Arsyian et al.'s (2019) opinion that if products do not have halal certification, the processed food and beverage products can be withdrawn from circulation by the Indonesian government. The SEHATI program is expected to help SMEs obtain halal certification, thereby assuring consumers that products with halal certification are guaranteed to be halal and safe. Sakti et al. (2021) state that the Indonesian government is ambitious to become the world's leading halal producer, leveraging the large Muslim population and high consumption of halal products.

1.1 Socialization of the Free Halal Certification Program (SEHATI)

The socialization of the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency aims to introduce and enhance the understanding of livestock processing SMEs about the SEHATI program. This socialization is expected to encourage and motivate livestock processing SMEs to register their products by utilizing the facilitation provided for free. Based on interview results, the socialization of the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency by LP3H Unisba and Uinma in collaboration with the Ministry of Religious Affairs (Kemenag) and the Cooperative Department (Dinkop) of Blitar Regency includes:

1. Delivery of materials on halal certification, halal ingredients, and the halal production process (PPH).
2. Introduction to the SEHATI program, the purpose, and objectives of the SEHATI program.
3. The application mechanism for the SEHATI program, requirements, terms, and benefits of participating in the SEHATI program.

The results of the SEHATI program socialization in Blitar Regency include:

1. Increased awareness among MSME actors regarding the importance of halal certification.
2. Increased participation of MSMEs in halal certification.
3. Increased number of MSME actors obtaining halal certification through the SEHATI program.

The research findings align with Ismail's opinion (2019), which states that socialization is one of the learning processes to understand the values or new programs that exist or emerge within society. The socialization of the SEHATI program has a close connection with the learning process to understand the values or new programs that exist or emerge within society.

1.2 Assistance for Free Halal Certification Program (SEHATI)

Anas et al. (2023) stated that to facilitate MSMEs in obtaining self-declaration statements, the assistance of PPH is needed to accompany MSMEs in obtaining halal certification through self-declaration. Based on the results of the SEHATI program assistance interviews in Blitar Regency conducted by P3H Unisba and Uinma under the auspices of LP3H Unisba and Uinma, many MSMEs engaged in livestock processing were unaware of the requirements, mechanisms, and procedures for applying for halal certification through the SEHATI program, hence the need for this assistance. The SEHATI program assistance in Blitar Regency can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Assistance in SEHATI Program Application

Through assistance provided to MSME actors in livestock processing, they become aware of the requirements, mechanisms, and procedures for applying for halal certification through the SEHATI program. The constraints felt by MSME actors in livestock processing lie in the issuance of halal certification, where there is a variation in the issuance time ranging from 7 days, 15 days, to even 1 month before issuance, due to several factors including:

1. Surge in demand for self-declared halal certification scheme resulting in longer verification processes
2. Completeness of the submitted application documents,
3. Complexity of the business, which may involve more complex production processes or require deeper inspections to ensure compliance with halal standards.

These research findings are consistent with the study by Rachman et al. (2023), which states that assistance greatly helps MSME actors who are not proficient in using technology so that the halal product process can be carried out effectively and can serve as an encouragement to assist the government in increasing the number of halal-certified MSME actors.

2. Evaluation of the Implementation of the Free Halal Certification Program (SEHATI)

The evaluation of the SEHATI program implementation aims to measure the extent of success achieved by MSME actors in livestock processing together with P3H based on a logic model evaluation, which includes: Input, activities, outputs, and outcomes.

2.1 Input in the Implementation of the SEHATI Program

Yuliani (2023) stated that several parties involved in the implementation of the SEHATI program include MSME actors who have utilized the SEHATI program, halal product process facilitators (P3H), and facilitation from the SEHATI program. The resources used in the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency include: MSME actors in livestock processing, P3H, and program facilitation. Based on the research results, the input aspects in the SEHATI program can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Average score of livestock MSME’s responses based on inputs in the SEHATI program

Statement	SDS	DS	A	SA	Average
1.1 Business actor					
1.1.1 SEHATI program goals	0	12,5	25	37,5	3,5
1.1.2 SEHATI program benefits	0	12,5	12,5	75	3,62
1.2 P3H tasks	0	25	25	50	3,62
1.3 SEHATI program facilitation	0	12,5	25	62,5	3,5
Average					3,56

Note: SDS (Strongly Disagree), DS (Disagree), A (Agree), SA (Strongly Agree)

Source : Processed primary data (2024)

From Table 1, it is evident that livestock MSMEs are highly aware of the inputs or resources in the SEHATI program such as goals, benefits, P3H tasks, and SEHATI program facilitation. Livestock MSMEs have a profound understanding of the benefits of the SEHATI program and the tasks of P3H in the SEHATI program. Understanding the benefits of the SEHATI program indicates that livestock MSMEs understand how the program can add value to their businesses, both in terms of product quality, consumer trust, and business sustainability. This is consistent with the findings of Larasati and Yasin (2024), who state that as understanding of halal certification and halal awareness increases, interest in halal certification among businesses also increases. The understanding of livestock MSMEs regarding the tasks of P3H includes checking documents for halal certification applications, verifying and validating halal statements submitted, and recommending halal product statements that meet halal standards. The understanding of livestock MSMEs regarding P3H tasks not only reflects awareness of the importance of compliance with halal standards but also demonstrates their motivation to support the halal certification process.

However, the goals and facilitation of the SEHATI program for livestock MSMEs received the lowest average score. The limitations faced by livestock MSMEs in terms of resources, whether financial, human resources, or knowledge about the halal certification process, can hinder their ability to implement the SEHATI program. This aligns with the views of Anggreani et al. (2013), who state that the most fundamental problems faced by MSME actors include a lack of human resources with knowledge and skills in business development, issues with financing, inadequate infrastructure and facilities, and limited access to product marketing.

2.2 Activities in the Implementation of the SEHATI Program

Activities in the implementation of the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency include socialization and assistance to livestock MSME actors. Based on the research results, it is shown that livestock MSME actors have a profound understanding of the activities in the SEHATI program, as indicated in Table 2.

Table 2. Average score of livestock MSME’s responses based on activities in the SEHATI Program

Statement	SDS	DS	A	SA	Average
2.1 SEHATI program socialization	0	12,5	37,5	50	3,37
2.2 SEHATI program assistance	0	12,5	50	37,5	3,25
Average					3,31

Note: SDS (Strongly Disagree), DS (Disagree), A (Agree), SA (Strongly Agree)

Source : Processed primary data (2024)

From Table 2, it is evident that livestock MSMEs have a profound understanding of the activities of the SEHATI program, namely socialization and assistance. The evaluation results of the SEHATI program activities show that livestock MSME actors give a score indicating a strong understanding of the socialization activities, which include a strong understanding of the importance of consuming halal products, the importance of halal certification for MSME actors, and the benefits and mechanisms of the self-declared halal certification program. This indicates that the socialization has been successful in delivering information clearly and effectively to livestock MSMEs, enabling them to have a good understanding of the concepts and procedures related to halal certification.

However, the indicator for assistance in the SEHATI program obtained the lowest average score. This indicates that although livestock MSME actors understand the concepts and procedures of halal certification, they face difficulties in implementing the practical steps required, such as registering an account through SiHalal, filling out documents, completing and submitting the Halal Product Assurance Letter (SJPH), and obtaining a Business Identification Number (NIB). Improvement or enhancement in assisting livestock MSME actors is needed to help them overcome these barriers and ensure that they can smoothly and efficiently follow the halal certification process. The research findings are in line with the study by Mahmud et al. (2023), which states that the lack of competence among MSME actors is noted by the government and needs to be improved through various schemes, one of which is intensive assistance.

2.3 Outputs in the Implementation of the SEHATI Program

Output of the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency was assessed based on the program activities that had been conducted and the program's targets. According to the research findings, livestock MSME actors strongly agreed with the output of the SEHATI program, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Average score of livestock MSMEs' responses based on outputs in the SEHATI program

Statement	SDS	DS	A	SA	Average
3.1 SEHATI program implemented	0	25	12,5	62,5	3,37
3.2 SEHATI program targets achieved	0	12,5	37,5	50	3,37
Average					3,37

Note: SDS (Strongly Disagree), DS (Disagree), A (Agree), SA (Strongly Agree)

Source : Processed primary data (2024)

Based on Table 3, the outputs or results of the SEHATI program and the program's targets received the same score, which was equal to the average score indicating strong agreement. The increase in awareness, understanding, compliance, and the number of halal products, as well as the improvement in product safety produced by livestock MSME actors, demonstrated the success of the SEHATI program in achieving its objectives and the good acceptance and understanding of the SEHATI program by livestock MSME actors. This was in line with the views of Akim et al. (2018), who stated that halal certification would ultimately increase consumer trust in MSME products, maintain positive relationships between the local community and MSMEs, and increase awareness of halal and haram products and the importance of halal certification for their products.

Outcomes in the Implementation of the SEHATI Program

The outcome of the activities and outputs from the implementation of the SEHATI program in Blitar Regency were viewed from short-term and long-term outcomes. Based on the research findings, livestock MSME actors strongly agreed with the outcome of the SEHATI program, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Average score of MSME actors' responses based on outcomes in the SEHATI program

Statement	SDS	DS	A	SA	Average
4.1 Short-term	0	0	50	50	3,5
4.2 Long-term	0	0	37,5	62,5	3,62
Average					3,56

Note: SDS (Strongly Disagree), DS (Disagree), A (Agree), SA (Strongly Agree)

Source: Processed primary data (2024)

Based on Table 4, it was known that the results of the SEHATI program implementation fell under the category of strongly agree. The evaluation of the SEHATI program results showed that livestock MSME actors gave a score of strongly agree regarding the long-term outcomes, indicating that they had a more mature vision and strategy for the growth and sustainability of their businesses in the longer term. This aligned with the views of Sayogya (2019), who stated that with the growing global market, food companies that utilized innovation effectively would lead the competition by gaining the right segments to achieve competitive advantages in the market.

Short-term outcome indicators in the SEHATI program obtained the lowest average score, indicating that challenges and obstacles needed to be addressed to ensure the success of the program implementation in the short term. The SEHATI program should focus more on efforts to improve socialization about the halal certification process, requirements in the SEHATI program, simplification of the certification process regarding registration procedures, reducing the number of documents required for halal certification, and increasing technical support such as providing consultation services related to the SEHATI program and providing periodic and sustainable assistance to ensure that livestock MSME actors truly understood the halal certification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The SEHATI program implemented in Blitar Regency provided significant benefits in increasing awareness, understanding, compliance, and the number of halal products among livestock MSME actors, especially those involved in processing. This indicated the effectiveness of the program in assisting livestock MSME actors in obtaining halal certification. Resource limitations and access to information were barriers in the implementation of this program. Livestock MSME actors understood the concept of halal certification but faced difficulties in practical steps such as document completion and registration. The increase in awareness, understanding, compliance, the number of halal products, and product safety signified the success of the SEHATI program in achieving its objectives, thus indicating good acceptance and understanding of the SEHATI program among livestock MSME actors.

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